

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of *para*-Substituted Anilines by Peroxomonosulphate

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Kinetics of oxidation of several *para*-substituted anilines by peroxomonosulphate (PMS) in aqueous acetic acid medium have been investigated. The reaction follows a total second order, first order each in [PMS] and [substrate]. The reaction rate is retarded by both electron-releasing and withdrawing groups. Absence of free radical formation is confirmed. Activation energy and thermodynamic parameters have been computed. A probable mechanism has been proposed.

Anilines have been oxidized by a number of oxidizing agents, such as permanganate¹, hydrogen peroxide², periodate³, epoxide⁴, peracetic acids⁵, peroxomonophosphoric acid⁶, peroxydisulfate⁷ depending on the experimental conditions. Although the mechanism of oxidation of aromatic amines by Caro's acid (PMS) has been investigated⁸, there is no kinetic work to establish the mechanism. In the present work, oxidation of anilines have been carried out in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of aniline with PMS is immeasurably fast in water. There is no reaction between aniline and PMS in the presence of mineral acids at various pH values (pH 3.4–5.0 maintained with acetic acid and sodium acetate buffer). This suggests that NH₂ is the reactive species and NH₃⁺ is inert towards PMS. In the acetic acid medium, there is equilibrium between the protonated and unprotonated species of aniline and unprotonated species reacts with PMS (hydrolysis for aniline acetate is 54%),

At constant ionic strength (0.3 mol dm⁻³) in 50% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid medium (pH 3.0), the order of reaction with respect to PMS is unity as shown by the linearity of log [PMS] vs time plots for over 75% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*₁) for various [PMS] at constant [aniline] are almost constant (Table 1). At different initial concentrations of aniline, the plots of log [PMS] vs time are found to be linear. A plot of log *k*₁ vs log [aniline] is linear with a slope of 1.01 ± 0.005 (*r* = 0.999) and a plot of *k*₁ vs [aniline] is also linear (*r* = 0.999) passing through the origin. This shows that the order is unity. Variation in ionic strength in the range 0.1–1.5 mol dm⁻³ (Na₂SO₄) has no effect on the reaction rate, indicating the ion-dipole type reaction.

The reactions of aniline with PMS were studied in varying proportions of acetic acid and water (20–80%, v/v) keeping all other concentrations constant. The rate is found

to decrease with decreasing dielectric constant of the solvent mixture, indicating that the reaction is between a dipole and an ion (Table 2). A plot of log *k*₁ vs 1/*D* results in a parabola rather than a straight-line at all temperatures.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF ANILINE WITH PMS

[HOAc] = 50% (v/v), temp. = 318 K, μ = 0.3 mol dm⁻³

10 ² [Aniline] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [PMS] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ <i>k</i> ₁ s ⁻¹	10 ² <i>k</i> ₂ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.5	2.0	0.276	5.52
1.0	2.0	0.563	5.63
2.0	2.0	1.140	5.70
3.0	2.0	1.770	5.54
4.0	2.0	2.180	5.36
5.0	2.0	2.780	5.53
5.0	2.0	2.810	5.62 ^a
6.0	2.0	3.360	5.60
7.0	2.0	3.860	5.51
8.0	2.0	4.500	5.62
5.0	1.0	2.860	5.72
5.0	3.0	2.760	5.52
5.0	4.0	2.850	5.70
5.0	5.0	2.800	5.60
5.0	5.0	2.820	5.64 ^a

^aContained 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

The oxidation of aniline, under nitrogen atmosphere, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate. Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. This was further confirmed by epr spectrum. This rules out the one-electron oxidation giving support to the polar mechanism.

The reaction between PMS and aniline under kinetic condition gave an insoluble residue when kept for ~3 h. The recrystallized residue in alcohol was found to be nitrosobenzene. It was established through the melting point determination (m.p. 60°) which corresponds to the literature data. Similar nitrosoproducts were obtained for

the *para*-substituted anilines. The products were confirmed by tlc. In the stoichiometry of the reaction, it is found that two moles of PMS react with one mole of aniline.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[Aniline] = 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [PMS] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.3$ mol dm⁻³

Acetic acid %(v/v)	Dielectric* constant	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)			
		298 K	308 K	318 K	328 K
20	78.5	2.89	10.00	29.0	58.7
30	72.0	2.13	6.51	21.6	44.1
40	63.3	1.92	4.87	15.0	34.8
50	56.0	1.62	4.30	12.0	27.5
60	45.5	1.38	3.73	10.5	22.4
70	38.5	1.28	3.37	09.4	20.3
80	27.0	1.22	3.08	08.4	18.4

*S. Kilpi and E. Lindell, *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicae, Ser. A II*, 1967, 136.

Mechanism and rate law : The experimental results suggests rate law (2),

$$\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{PMS}] [\text{aniline}] \quad (2)$$

The formation of a S_N2 intermediate by nucleophilic attack of the amine lone-pair (in aniline) on the electrophilic peroxoxygen of PMS is supposed to be the rate-limiting step. There is a formation of cyclic transition state⁸. The ionization of PMS into HO⁺ and SO₄²⁻ and the attack of the lone-pair of electron of nitrogen with HO⁺ takes place simultaneously forming a transition complex of cyclic nature. This intermediate decomposes to the phenylhydroxylamine,

The phenylhydroxylamine is oxidized by another molecule of PMS to give nitro compound, which on elimination of water molecule gives nitrosobenzene,

The proposed mechanism is in agreement with observation that the peroxides act as electrophiles in reactions with electron pair donors⁹.

Substituent effects : For better understanding of the mechanism and the nature of the transition state, kinetics of oxidation of thirteen *para*-substituted-anilines were investigated. The second order rate constants ($k_2 = k_1/[\text{substrate}]$) for the substituted-anilines together with the activation parameters are given in Table 3. The results indicate that both electron-releasing and electron-withdrawing substituents decrease the reaction rate. No simple Hammett relation is found for the substituent effects. Since protonation of NH₂ group occurs in the presence of the solvent acetic acid, the availability of free NH₂ site for the oxidation reaction is less. Hence there is decrease in rate. The low rate constants for the halogen substituted anilines indicate that both the mesomeric and the *d*-orbital resonance may be operative^{10,11}. For the electron-withdrawing groups, due to resonance hybrid, the electron density of the unshared pair on nitrogen of the NH₂ is lowered making it non-available for PMS to react¹². For the nitro-substituted aniline there is a small decrease in rate due to cross-conjugation involving NO₂ and the reaction centre¹³. The very high rate constant for the diploar sulphanilic acid has no simple explanation.

Since there is no significant correlation with any single parameter substituent constants, the rates were analyzed in terms of the dual substituent parameters¹⁴. The rates were correlated with σ_1 and four different σ_R values in Taft's equation. The multiple correlation *R*, the standard deviation

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ANILINE-PMS SYSTEM

Substituent	$10^3 k_2$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)				<i>E_a</i> kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	298K	308K	318K	328K				
<i>p</i> -H	9.00	24.4	56.1	125	72.2	69.6	51.6	85.4
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	2.53	06.83	17.6	40.1	75.1	72.5	48.2	89.9
<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	3.56	09.57	23.6	49.3	71.5	68.9	60.1	87.8
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	5.43	15.60	34.8	81.8	73.2	70.6	51.9	86.7
<i>p</i> -F	4.25	13.00	31.1	71.6	76.1	73.5	43.3	87.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.15	04.99	11.1	26.0	67.2	64.6	77.4	89.4
<i>p</i> -Br	1.68	03.77	09.0	19.2	66.7	64.1	80.9	90.1
<i>p</i> -I	1.48	03.20	07.7	18.5	68.6	66.0	74.6	90.4
<i>p</i> -COOH	5.47	14.20	36.5	77.6	72.4	69.8	54.3	86.7
<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅	5.21	13.70	32.1	71.5	66.8	64.2	75.4	85.9
<i>p</i> -COCH ₃	4.95	12.30	28.4	60.3	67.8	65.2	71.2	87.2
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	8.11	18.60	42.1	65.0	57.6	55.0	99.9	86.3
<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	24.50	53.00	108.0	208.0	58.0	55.4	89.3	83.5

SD and F distribution were used as the criteria of goodness of fit (Table 4). In all cases no satisfactory results were obtained.

TABLE 4—CORRELATION OF THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF *para*-SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY PMS WITH DUAL SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS AT 298 K

Substituent constant	ρ_I	ρ_R	R	SD	F
σ_I, σ_R^O	-3.78	-2.62	0.6737	0.22	19.95
σ_I, σ_R^{BA}	-3.81	-2.78	0.6194	0.24	14.94
σ_I, σ_R^-	-3.83	-2.83	0.6138	0.24	14.51
σ_I, σ_R^+	-3.82	-2.76	0.6536	0.23	17.90

The activation energies were obtained from the plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$. From this, the entropy, enthalpy and free energy of activation were calculated. The decrease in entropy may be due to the ordered arrangement of acetate ion with water molecule in the reaction mixture through hydrogen bonds. This leads to the loss of freedom and decrease in the basicity of aniline that is responsible for the reaction with PMS¹⁵. The existence of a linear relationship between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger ($r = 0.978$) indicates that a single mechanism is operating throughout the series¹⁶. The isokinetic temperature was evaluated as 346 K.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of the purest analytical samples except *p*-aminobenzoic acid and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate which were prepared by standard methods. Potassium peroxomonosulphate was obtained from Du Pont Chemical Co., U.S.A.; it is known by the trade name 'Oxone'.

The solid samples were used as such and liquid samples were distilled just before use. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromium trioxide and distilled.

The experiments were carried out in 50% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid medium at constant ionic strength (0.3 mol dm⁻³) in the temperature range 298–328 K. The reactions

were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions taking [aniline] in excess. Effects of variations of [oxidant], [substrate], ionic strength and dielectric constant were studied. The progress of the reaction was followed by iodometric determination of the unreacted oxidant present in the aliquots of the reaction mixture at different time intervals. The rate constants were calculated from the plots of \log [PMS] vs time by least-squares method. All the kinetic runs were carried out in duplicate and the results are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

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